

NEWSLETTER

CONCILIARE: keep up with the project's achievements!

Welcome to the eighth edition of our newsletter!

We are pleased to share with the CONCILIARE community some of our recent updates from various Work Packages and institutions, including new publications, events, and partnerships that have helped amplify our social and academic impact. Enjoy reading!

PUBLICATIONS

Van Nieuwenhuysse, K., Bentravato, D., & Valentim, J. P. (2026). **The colonial past and/in history textbooks: A literature review.** Current Opinion in Psychology 2026, 68:102264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2025.102264>

Zian, Y., Bosuma, A., Chevalier, A., & Licata, L. (2026). **Restitution actée, réparation ratée. La Belgique et ses contradictions postcoloniales.** Relations Internationales, e204, p. 69-82. <https://doi.org/10.3917/ri.204.0069>

PAST EVENTS

CONCILIARE's second annual meeting

From January 28 to 31, our second annual meeting brought us together at the Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), in Brussels. Over four intense and inspiring days, members from different countries and institutions shared their work across all Work Packages and engaged in meaningful discussions about the project's progress and next steps.

The meeting took place within the conference "Colonial Legacies in Belgium", organized in partnership with the HERICOL project, and had the participation of the COLUMN project. This was a great opportunity to connect with scholars and professionals from diverse backgrounds, exchange perspectives on colonial heritage, and gather valuable insights for the future.

II International Colloquium Rethink Latin America

From February 25 to 27, the University of Minho hosted the II International Colloquium "Rethink Latin America - Decoloniality, Interculturality and New Subjectivities". The event offered interdisciplinary and cross-border dialogue, bringing together people from different countries to discuss urgent issues. Both in person and online, participants shared intersectional perspectives on colonial histories, decolonial approaches, memory, gender, culture, communication and much more. The CONCILIARE project played a key role in organizing the event and moderating the debates,

with the dedicated involvement of project members and collaborators such as Emiliano Abad, Isabel Macedo, Fernando Gonçalves, Luiza Lins, Rosa Cabecinhas, and Sebastián Zuñiga.

This event results from a partnership between the Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL) and the University of Minho, in cooperation with the CONCILIARE Project, the Association of Philosophy and Liberation (AFYL), the Center for Iberian and Ibero-American Studies (CEIIBA), the Communication and Society Research Centre (CECS), and the Laboratory for Discourse Studies (LED).

“Healing bodies, repairing wounds?” with Laurent Licata and Giovanna Leone

On January 23, Laurent Licata and Giovanna Leone were invited to speak at the concluding panel of the international meetings *“Preserve Human Remains”*, held at the Quai Branly Museum in Paris. The roundtable “Healing bodies, repairing wounds?” addressed critical questions surrounding the conservation of human remains still held in museums, particularly those present in European institutions as a result of colonial violence. During their intervention, they also presented the CONCILIARE project and its purposes.

“Between bars and politics: art as a form of resistance and intervention”

As part of the program of the 1^o National Meeting of Social Sciences Students, which took place in the University of Coimbra on 28 November 2025, Joaquim Pires Valentim moderated the panel “Between bars and politics: art as a form of resistance and intervention”. The activity brought together artists and scholars to discuss how art can be an important tool to transform society.

UPCOMING EVENTS

House of European History: New Exhibition “Postcolonial?”

We are happy to introduce our new partnership with the House of European History, a museum in Brussels! Working together will amplify CONCILIARE’s impact and help translate our research results into concrete policies and social change.

On April 17, the museum will inaugurate the exhibition “Postcolonial?”, which will be on display until 14 March 2027. Through contemporary artworks, historical objects, and personal stories, the exhibition offers a necessary European reckoning with colonialism, questioning how the colonial matrix of power – the ideas, events, inequalities, and injustices born of colonialism – continues to shape the modern world. Throughout the exhibition, there will be co-created activities with invited artists, scholars, activists, and cultural practitioners to foster public dialogue, creative experimentation, and inclusive participation. We hope to see you all there!

Book Launch & Research Presentation: WP2 Study on the Decolonization of Public Space

On March 23, Yasmina Zian will present findings from the research conducted in Work Package 2. The presentation will take place as part of the launch of the collective book “*Place Names in Brussels: Past and Present Issues*”, directed by Iadine Degryse, Benjamin Wayens, Chantal Kesteloot, Dennis De Vriese, and Matthijs Degraeve.

The article examines the Pétillon train station in Brussels, revisiting the different approaches to the decolonization of public space that have emerged in the city since the early 2000s. Participation in the event is free of charge, but registration is required. [Click here](#) to know more.

Call for Papers: “Colonialism and Public Space: Memories in Dispute”

CONCILIARE members Pedro Menezes, Alana Castro de Azevedo, and Sebastián Zuñiga are coordinating the next special issue of the *Lusophone Journal of Cultural Studies*, which will focus on colonialism, public space, and collective memory.

The publication invites submissions that explore a wide range of topics related to the (de)colonisation of public space. Both theoretical and empirical contributions are welcome from the humanities, social sciences, arts, and creative fields.

The submission deadline (Portuguese or English) is **15 May 2026**.

To access the full call for papers, [click here](#).

REMEMBERING

CONCILIARE's kick off meeting: two years ago!

In March 2024, the CONCILIARE kick-off meeting took place in Rome, laying the foundations for the project. The event brought together at Sapienza University researchers from the institutions that make up the consortium, along with external experts and members of the European Research Executive Agency.

The photos below (© Giuseppe Follacchio) show moments from the decolonial tour of the city, guided by Silvano Falocco, co-author with Carlo Boumis of *Roma Coloniale*, a book that maps the colonial traces left in Rome during the fascist era.

Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Paula Di Leone, Rosa Cabecinhas, Isabel Macedo, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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